

Stability of Libration Points Around $L_{4,5}$ with Oblateness Primaries and Circumbinary Disc in Elliptic Restricted Three-Body Problem

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Abstract

The present paper considers the restricted three-body problem (R3BP) in elliptic framework when both primaries are oblate spheroids and enclosed by a circumbinary disc. The investigation has been carried out both analytically and numerically, the effects of oblateness of the primaries together with the gravitational potential from a disc on the triangular equilibrium $L_{4,5}$ and their linear stability of the system, The effect of the oblateness of the more massive primary, circumbinary disc and eccentricity on the location of triangular points show a move towards the line joining the primaries while increase in oblateness of less massive primary causes a significant shift towards the origin on ξ - axis. All the perturbations reduces the range of stability $0 < \mu < \mu_c$ of the triangular points, except gravitational potential from the disc which increases the stability region, Where μ_c is the critical mass parameter depends on the parameters involved, which shows that circumbinary disc has stabilizing tendency.

Keywords: Elliptic restricted three-body problem - Circumbinary disc - Oblate

1. Introduction

The elliptic restricted three - body problem (ER3BP) describes the dynamics of a body with negligible mass moving in the gravitational field of two finite bodies (m_1 and m_2), called the primaries, which revolve around their common centre of mass on elliptic orbits which is in line with the laws of motion of the two - body problem. A typical example is the motion of Earth - Moon system together with an artificial satellite constitutes such problem. The ER3BP posses five points of equilibrium; three collinear and two triangular, The collinear points are generally unstable while the triangular points are stable for the mass ratio less than 0.03852 (Szebehely 1967). The bodies of the elliptic restricted three - body problems are generally considered to be spherical in shape, but in actual situations, It is observed that several bodies in the solar system (e.g; Earth, Jupiter and Saturn) and in the stellar system (e.g; Regulus, Luyten areerther , archid and altair) are sufficiently oblate. This oblateness of a body can produce deviations from the two - body motion. This motivates many researchers to include the effect of oblateness in their study Singh and Ishwar (1999); Aboulmagd 2012; Singh and Umar (2012); Singh and Taura (2013) and Singh and Taura (2014). In the stellar system planet formation occurs around young stars in disc that are rich in gas and dust. Also debris disc or circumstellar disc have been found around many

nearby stars (e.g; Ruchbah, HD 98800, Kepler 16, ϵ - Eradani e.t.c). Greaves et al. (1998) regarded the rings of dust particle as the young analogues of the kuiper belt. The solar system's own kuiper belt may be analogue to these circumstellar disc (Luu & Jewitt 2002). The orbit of most celestial bodies are elliptic rather than circular as such; the elliptical restricted three - body problem describes the dynamical system more accurately. This justifies the inclusion of the effects of gravitational potential from the disc on the motion of the infinitesimal mass in the study of ER3BP. The structure of the dynamical system would be quite different led to the existence of new equilibrium points under certain conditions due the influence of the ring - type circular cluster of material points (Jiang and Yeh 2003; Yeh and Jiang 2006; Kushvah 2008; Singh and Taura 2013). Kushvah (2008) studied both numerically and analytically the effects of radiation pressure of the more massive primary, oblateness of the less massive primary together with gravitational potential from circular cluster of material points on the linear stability of equilibrium points in the R3BP. Then Singh and Taura (2013) investigate the combined effects of oblateness of the primaries and radiation pressure of both primaries, together with gravitational potential from the disc in the framework of circular restricted three - body problem (in brief CR3BP). Later, in (2014) they extent the work by considering the effect of oblateness of the less massive primary up to zonal harmonic (J_4) and radiation pressure of the more massive primary surrounded by a circumbinary disk in frame of CR3BP; they found the triangular points are stable in $0 < \mu < \mu_c$ and unstable for $\mu_c < \mu < \frac{1}{2}$, Where μ_c is affected by the perturbing forces. The present work is organized as: Section 1, is the introduction; section 2 provides the equations of motion and locations of the triangular equilibrium solution; while sections 3 and 4 focuses on their linear stability and numerical application respectively, the discussions and conclusion are drawn in 5 and 6 respectively.

2. Equations of Motion

The equations of motion of the elliptic restricted three body problem (ER3BP) when both primaries are oblate spheroids surrounded by a circumbinary disc in a dimensionless, pulsating (rotating) coordinate system are given as;

$$\begin{aligned}\xi'' - 2\eta' &= \Omega_\xi, \\ \eta'' + 2\xi' &= \Omega_\eta, \\ \zeta'' &= \Omega_\zeta.\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

With the force function

$$\Omega = \frac{1}{(1-e^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \left[\frac{\xi^2 + \eta^2}{2} + \frac{1}{n^2} \left\{ \frac{(1-\mu)}{r_1} + \frac{\mu}{r_2} + \frac{(1-\mu)A_1}{2r_1^3} + \frac{\mu A_2}{2r_2^3} + \frac{M_b}{(r^2 + T^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right\} \right] \quad (2)$$

The mean motion, n , is given by

$$n^2 = \frac{1}{a} \left(1 + \frac{3e^2}{2} + \frac{3A_1}{2} + \frac{3A_2}{2} + \frac{2M_b r_c}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$r_i^2 = (\xi - \xi_i)^2 + \eta^2 + \zeta^2 \quad i = 1,2; \quad \xi_1 = -\mu \quad \xi_2 = (1 - \mu) \quad (4)$$

Where $\frac{M_b}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}$ is the potential from the circumbinary disc (Miyamoto & Nagai 1975, Singh and

Taura 2014); M_b is the total mass of the disc, $T = b + d$, b and d are parameter which determine the density profile of the circular cluster of material points. The parameter b controls the flatness of the profile and is known as the flatness parameter. The parameter d controls the size of the core of the density profile and is called the core parameter when $b=d=0$, the potential becomes that of a point mass, r_c is the radial distance of the infinitesimal body in the classical restricted and is given by $r_c^2 = 1 - \mu + \mu^2$. Then, the masses of the bigger and smaller primaries are m_1 and m_2 and m is the infinitesimal mass. The sum of the masses of the primaries and their separation distance are unity. Hence, $m_1 = 1 - \mu$, $m_2 = \mu$ where $0 < \mu = \frac{m_2}{m_1 + m_2} \leq \frac{1}{2}$ is the mass ratio; A_i , ($i = 1,2$) are the oblateness coefficient of the smaller and bigger primary; r_i , ($i = 1,2$) are the distances of the infinitesimal mass from the bigger and smaller primaries, respectively; while a and e are respectively the semi-major axis and eccentricity of the orbits.

3. Locations of the Triangular Equilibrium Points

The equilibrium solutions of the problem are determined by equating all velocities and accelerations of the dynamical system to zero. The equilibrium points are solutions of $\Omega_\xi = \Omega_\eta = \Omega_\zeta = 0$, it yield,

$$\xi n^2 - \left\{ \frac{(1-\mu)(\xi+\mu)}{r_1^3} + \frac{\mu(\xi+\mu-1)}{r_2^3} + \frac{3(1-\mu)(\xi+\mu)A_1}{2r_1^5} + \frac{3\mu A_2(\xi+\mu-1)}{2r_2^5} + \frac{M_b \xi}{(r^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right\} = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\eta \left[1 - \frac{1}{n^2} \left\{ \frac{(1-\mu)}{r_1^3} + \frac{\mu}{r_2^3} + \frac{3(1-\mu)A_1}{2r_1^5} + \frac{3\mu A_2}{2r_2^5} + \frac{M_b}{(r^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right\} \right] = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\zeta \left\{ \frac{(1-\mu)}{r_1^3} + \frac{\mu}{r_2^3} + \frac{3(1-\mu)A_1}{2r_1^5} + \frac{3\mu A_2}{2r_2^5} + \frac{M_b}{(r^2+T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right\} = 0$$

The triangular points solutions of the dynamical system are solutions equations of (5) and (6) with $\eta \neq 0$ give the positions of the triangular points $L_{4,5}$. Which we obtain

$$n^2 = \frac{1}{r_1^3} + \frac{3A_1}{2r_1^5} + \frac{M_b}{(r^2+T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}$$

$$n^2 = \frac{1}{r_2^3} + \frac{3A_2}{2r_2^5} + \frac{M_b}{(r^2+T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (7)$$

Neglecting the effects of oblateness of the primaries and the potential from the disc ($A_1=A_2=M_b=0$), the equations are reduced to

$$n^2 = \frac{1}{r_1^3}$$

$$n^2 = \frac{1}{r_2^3} \quad (8)$$

These values change slightly by $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2$ (say), with the introduction of oblateness, so that

$$r_1 = \frac{1}{n^{\frac{2}{3}}} + \varepsilon_1, \quad r_2 = \frac{1}{n^{\frac{2}{3}}} + \varepsilon_2, \quad \varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2 \ll 1 \quad (9)$$

Equating (3) together with $A_1=A_2=M_b=0$ and (9) yield,

$$r_1 = (a)^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(1 - \frac{e^2}{2} \right) + \varepsilon_1$$

$$r_2 = (a)^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(1 - \frac{e^2}{2} \right) + \varepsilon_2 \quad (10)$$

From (7), (8), and (9) and neglecting higher order terms in $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, A_2$ and e^2 we get

$$\varepsilon_1 = \frac{-(a)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{2} \left(A_1 + A_2 - A_1(a)^{\frac{-2}{3}} + \frac{2M_b(2r_c-a)}{3(r_c^2+T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = \frac{-(a)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{2} \left(A_1 + A_2 - A_2(a)^{\frac{-2}{3}} + \frac{2M_b(2r_c-a)}{3(r_c^2+T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) \quad (11)$$

Substituting for ε_1 and ε_2 in (10), we obtain

$$r_1^2 = (a)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 - e^2 - A_1 - A_2 + A_1(a)^{\frac{-2}{3}} - \frac{2M_b(2r_c-a)}{3(r_c^2-T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right)$$

$$r_2^2 = (a)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 - e^2 - A_1 - A_2 + A_2(a)^{\frac{-2}{3}} - \frac{2M_b(2r_c - a)}{3(r_c^2 - T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) \quad (12)$$

Making use of equations (4) and (12), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \xi &= \frac{1}{2} - \mu + \frac{1}{2} \left[(a)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 - e^2 - A_1 - A_2 + A_1(a)^{\frac{-2}{3}} - \frac{2M_b(2r_c - a)}{3(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) - (a)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 - e^2 - A_1 - A_2 + \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. A_2(a)^{\frac{-2}{3}} - \frac{2M_b(2r_c - a)}{3(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) \right] \\ \eta &= \pm \left[(a)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 - e^2 - A_1 - A_2 + A_1(a)^{\frac{-2}{3}} - \frac{2M_b(2r_c - a)}{3(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) - \frac{1}{4} \left(1 + 2(a)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 - e^2 - A_1 - A_2 + \right. \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \left. A_1(a)^{\frac{-2}{3}} - \frac{2M_b(2r_c - a)}{3(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) - 2a^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 - e^2 - A_1 - A_2 + A_2(a)^{\frac{-2}{3}} - \frac{2M_b(2r_c - a)}{3(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

The location of triangular points $L_{4,5} (\xi, \pm\eta)$ are given by (13).

4. Investigation of Linear Stability of the Triangular Points

The investigation of the linear stability of an infinitesimal body near the triangular points, we consider the characteristic equation giving by Singh and Umar (2012) as

$$\lambda^4 - (\Omega_{\eta\eta}^0 + \Omega_{\xi\xi}^0 - 4)\lambda^2 + \Omega_{\xi\xi}^0\Omega_{\eta\eta}^0 - (\Omega_{\xi\eta}^0)^2 = 0 \quad (15)$$

At the equilibrium points, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{\xi\xi}^0 &= \frac{1}{(1-e^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \left[\frac{3}{4(a)^{\frac{2}{3}}} + A_2 \left(\frac{9\mu}{4a^{\frac{2}{3}}} - \frac{3(1-\mu)}{4(a)^{\frac{2}{3}}} \right) + e^2 \left(\frac{3(1-\mu)}{4(a)^{\frac{2}{3}}} + \frac{3\mu}{4a^{\frac{2}{3}}} \right) + \frac{M_b(4r_c - 5a)}{4(a)^{\frac{2}{3}}(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{3M_b a \left(\frac{1}{4} - \mu + \mu^2 \right)}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \right] \\ \Omega_{\eta\eta}^0 &= \frac{1}{(1-e^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \left[3 - \frac{3}{4a^{\frac{2}{3}}} + A_2 \left(\frac{3(1-\mu)}{4(a)^{\frac{2}{3}}} + \frac{3\mu}{4a^{\frac{2}{3}}} \right) + e^2 \left(\frac{-3(1-\mu)}{4(a)^{\frac{2}{3}}} - \frac{3\mu}{4a^{\frac{2}{3}}} \right) + \frac{M_b a^{\frac{-2}{3}} (4r_c - 5a + 12a^{\frac{5}{3}})}{4(a)^{\frac{2}{3}}(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{3M_b a \left(a^{\frac{2}{3}} - \frac{1}{4} \right)}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \right] \\ \Omega_{\xi\eta}^0 &= \frac{1}{(1-e^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \eta \left[\frac{3(1-2\mu)}{2(a)^{\frac{2}{3}}} + A_2 \left(-\frac{3\mu}{a^{\frac{2}{3}}} \right) + e^2 \left(\frac{3(1-\mu)}{2(a)^{\frac{2}{3}}} - \frac{3\mu}{2a^{\frac{2}{3}}} \right) + \frac{3M_b(1-2\mu)(4r_c - 5a)}{6(a)^{\frac{2}{3}}(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{3M_b a \left(\frac{1}{2} - \mu \right)}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Putting the values above in the characteristic equation (15) and considering only the linear terms in e^2 , A_1 , A_2 , M_b and α for $a = 1 - \alpha$ we obtain

$$4(\lambda^2)^2 + 4(4 - 3\phi_1)\lambda^2 + 27\mu(1 - \mu) + 4\phi_2 = 0 \quad (16)$$

Where

$$\phi_1 = 1 + \mu A_2 + \frac{1}{2}e^2 - \frac{M_b}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{M_b r_c^2}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}}$$

And

$$\phi_2 = 3\mu(1 - \mu)\alpha + \frac{45}{4}\mu(1 - \mu)e^2 + 9\mu(1 - \mu)A_2 + \frac{3\mu(1 - \mu)M_b(4r_c - 11)}{2(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{27\mu(1 - \mu)M_b}{4(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}}$$

Equation (16) is a polynomial of degree two in λ^2 , with the use of quadratic formula we obtain

$$\lambda^2 = \frac{-(4 - 3\phi_1) \pm \sqrt{(4 - 3\phi_1)^2 - 27\mu(1 - \mu) - 4\phi_2}}{2}$$

For the motion to be stable, λ has to be pure imaginary so that we have bounded and periodic motion so we choose μ , ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 such that $\lambda^2 < 0$. Here, we obtain

$$3\phi_1 - 4 \leq 0$$

And the discriminant

$$\Delta = (4 - 3\phi_1)^2 - 27\mu(1 - \mu) - 4\phi_2 > 0, \quad \text{Produces,} \quad (17)$$

$$0 < e \leq \left[1 - \frac{9}{16} \left(1 + \mu A_2 - \frac{M_b}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{M_b r_c^2}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (18)$$

When $A_1 = A_2 = M_b = 0$, equation (18) becomes

$$0 < e \leq \frac{\sqrt{7}}{4} \quad (19)$$

If (19) is not satisfied, this means the roots of equation (14) will be either real or complex conjugate leading to the instability of the investigated points.

Now, from (17) we have

$$\Delta = \left(27 + 12\alpha + 45e^2 + 36A_2 + \frac{6M_b(4r_c - 11)}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{27M_b}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \right) \mu^2 - \left(27 + 12\alpha + 45e^2 + 42A_2 + \frac{6M_b(4r_c - 11)}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{27M_b}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \right) \mu + \left(1 - 3e^2 + \frac{6M_b}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} - \frac{6M_b r_c^2}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \right) \quad (20)$$

When $\Delta = 0$, we have the critical value of the mass parameter μ_c given by (21).

$$\mu_c = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{23}{27}} \right) - \frac{1}{9} \left(1 + \frac{13}{\sqrt{69}} \right) A_1 + \frac{1}{9} \left(1 - \frac{13}{\sqrt{69}} \right) A_2 - \frac{4}{27\sqrt{69}} \alpha - \frac{14}{9\sqrt{69}} e^2 + \left[\frac{(76 - 8r_c)(r_c^2 + T^2)}{27\sqrt{69}} - \frac{1 + 6r_c^2}{3\sqrt{69}} \right] \frac{M_b}{(r_c^2 + T^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \quad (21)$$

Equation (21) shows the effects of the oblateness, gravitational potential from a disc, the semi-major axis and the eccentricity on the orbits on the size of the region of stability.

5. Numerical Application of the System

The triangular points and critical mass parameter given by (13) and (21) of the problem are obtained numerically and graphically given in tables 1- 5 and figures 1 - 9.

Figure.1: The effect of the circumbinary disc (M_b) on the size of the region of stability for $A_2 = 0.02, T = 0.01, A_1 = 0.01$ and $a = 0.9$

Figure 2: showing changes in the size of the region of stability as the semi-major axis (a) changes for $A_2 = 0.02, T = 0.02, M_b = 0.01$ and $A_1 = 0.01$

Figure 3: Showing the decrease in size of the region of stability with increase in oblateness of the smaller primary (A_2) for $a = 0.8, T = 0.02, M_b = 0.01$ and $A_1 = 0.01$

Figure 4: showing the decrease in size of the region of stability with increase in oblateness of the bigger primary (A_2) for $a = 0.8, T = 0.02, M_b = 0.01$ and $A_1 = 0.01$

Table 1: Effect of semi-major axis on the triangular points and stability of the system for $e = 0.25, A_1 = 0.01, A_2 = 0.02, M_b = 0.01, T = 0.02$

	a	ξ	$\pm\eta$	μ_c
Classical Circular	1.0	0.25	0.866025	0.0385209
Classical Elliptic	0.95	0.25	0.809928	0.0259250
Perturbed Cases	0.90	0.245	0.756002	0.0202636
	0.85	0.245	0.734309	0.0193719
	0.80	0.245	0.711491	0.0184801
	0.75	0.245	0.687416	0.0175884
	0.70	0.245	0.661886	0.0166966
	0.65	0.245	0.634660	0.0158049
	0.60	0.245	0.605429	0.0149132

0.55	0.245	0.573781	0.0140214
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Table 2: Effect of the circumbinary disc on the triangular points and stability of the system for $e = 0.25$, $A_1 = 0.01$, $A_2 = 0.02$, $a = 0.90$, $T = 0.01$

	M_b	ξ	$\pm\eta$	μ_c
Classical Circular	0	0.25	0.866025	0.0385209
Classical Elliptic	0	0.25	0.789876	0.0250322
Perturbed Cases	0.001	0.245	0.781139	0.0209503
	0.01	0.245	0.776714	0.0211540
	0.1	0.245	0.730996	0.0231919
	0.2	0.245	0.676584	0.0254562
	0.3	0.245	0.617395	0.0277206
	0.4	0.245	0.551894	0.0298490
	0.5	0.245	0.477491	0.0322492

Table 3: Effect of eccentricity on the triangular points and stability for $M_b = 0.01$, $A_1 = 0.01$, $A_2 = 0.02$, $a = 0.6$, $T = 0.01$

	e	ξ	$\pm\eta$	μ_c
Classical Circular	0.0	0.25	0.866025	0.0385209
Classical Elliptic	0.01	0.25	0.679196	0.0313682
Perturbed Cases	0.10	0.245	0.663428	0.0256351
	0.15	0.245	0.656692	0.0232942
	0.20	0.245	0.647144	0.0200171
	0.25	0.245	0.634657	0.0158036
	0.30	0.245	0.619053	0.0106537
	0.35	0.245	0.600089	0.0045676

Table 4: Effect of the oblateness of the more massive primary on the triangular points and their stability $A_2 = 0.02$, $M_b = 0.01$, $a = 0.5$, $T = 0.01$, $e = 0.3$

	A_1	ξ	η	μ_c
Classical Circular	0.0	0.25	0.866025	0.0385209
Classical Elliptic	0.0	0.25	0.568563	0.0127494
Perturbed Cases	0.0001	0.24005	0.556270	0.0116912
	0.0010	0.24050	0.559523	0.0114352
	0.0015	0.24075	0.559465	0.0112927
	0.0100	0.24500	0.558477	0.0088702
	0.0150	0.24770	0.557894	0.0074452

Table 5: Effect of the oblateness of the less massive primary on the triangular points and stability for $M_b = 0.01$, $A_1 = 0.01$, $e = 0.3$, $a = 0.90$, $T = 0.01$

	A_2	ξ	$\pm\eta$	μ_c
Classical Circular	0.0	0.25	0.866025	0.0385209
Classical Elliptic	0.0	0.25	0.773482	0.0198834
Perturbed Cases	0.0002	0.2549	0.765642	0.0172472
	0.0020	0.2540	0.765134	0.0171342
	0.0025	0.2538	0.764992	0.0171028
	0.0100	0.2500	0.762871	0.0166320
	0.0150	0.2475	0.761453	0.0163181
	0.1000	0.2050	0.736937	0.0109818
	0.1500	0.1800	0.722128	0.0078428
	0.2000	0.1550	0.707008	0.0047039

Figure 5: Showing the effect of Oblateness of the bigger primary on the locations of the triangular points.

Figure 6: Showing the effect of eccentricity on the locations of the triangular points.

Figure 7: Showing the effect of the disc on the locations of the triangular points.

Figure 8: Showing the effect of oblateness of the smaller primary on the locations of the triangular points.

Figure 9: Showing the effect of semi-major axis on the locations of the triangular points.

5. Discussion

This paper presents a study of motion of a test particle around triangular equilibrium points of the restricted problem of three - body under the effects of oblateness of the primaries, eccentricity and circumbinary disc. The locations of the triangular points $L_{4,5}$ are found to be affected by oblateness of the primaries, semi - major axis, eccentricity and circumbinary disc. The effects of oblateness, semi - major axis, eccentricity and circumbinary disc on the positions of the triangular points and stability are shown numerically Tables 1 - 5 and graphically Figures 1 - 9. In Table 1 and Figure 9 decrease in the value of semi - major axis cause shift toward the line joining the primaries. While Tables 2 - 5 and Figures 5 - 8 show that increase in circumbinary disc, eccentricity and oblateness of the primaries cause $L_{4,5}$ to move toward the line joining the primaries. And it also observed that increase in oblateness of the primaries led to a significant shift towards the origin on the ξ - axis. Equation (13) is in accordance with Singh and Umar (2012) in the absence of radiation pressure in their work and neglecting circumbinary disc in ours. In the circular case (i.e., $e = 0$ and $a = 1$), Our result is in agreement with Singh and Taura (2013) when the primaries are non - luminous in their work. It also confirm Singh and Taura (2014) in the absence of oblateness up to the zonal (i.e., $B_2 = 0$), (13) fully agree with Singh and Ishwar (1999); On ignoring the circumbinary disc and oblateness of the less massive primary (i.e., $A_2 = M_b = 0$), neglecting all the perturbations (i.e., $A_1 = A_2 = M_b = 0$) the classical case of Szebehely (1967) is obtained.

The critical mass parameter μ_c given by equation (20) depends on the oblateness of the primaries, eccentricity of the orbits, semi – major axis and gravitational potential form circumbinary disc. The effects of the said parameters on the region of stability can be known by equation (20). Equation (20) confirms the result of Singh and Umar (2012) (i.e., $M_b = 0$ and in their work when $q_1 = q_2 = 1$). It also seen that, equation (20) and Figure 1 increase in gravitational potential from the disc leading to the increase in the size of the region of stability which posses a stabilizing tendency which is in agreement with the findings of Singh and Taura (2014). And Figures 2 - 4 that the size of stability decrease with the increase in the value of oblateness coefficient, eccentricity and semi - major axis which they possess a destabilizing tendency which validates the findings of Singh and Umar (2012).

6. Conclusion

The existence and stability of equilibrium points in the framework of elliptic R3BP has been studied under the effects of oblateness of the primaries, semi - major axis, eccentricity and circumbinary disc. The locations of triangular points $L_{4,5}$ are found which were affected by the aforementioned parameters. The triangular points are stable for $0 < \mu < \mu_c$; μ_c is the critical mass parameter influenced by the aforesaid parameters. The effects of the circumbinary disc, oblateness of the more massive primary and eccentricity on the location of triangular points show a move towards the line joining the primaries while increase in oblateness of less massive primary causes

a significant shift to the origin of ξ - axis. All the perturbations have destabilizing tendency except the circumbinary disc which increase the stability region.

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